

1 A Wind Chart to Characterize Potential Offshore Wind Energy Sites

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12
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14 Marine Wind.

15
16 **Abstract**

17 Offshore wind industry needs to improve wind assessment in order to decrease the
18 uncertainty associated to wind resource and its influence on financial requirements.
19 Here, several features related to offshore wind resource assessment are discussed, such
20 as input wind data, estimation of long-term and extreme wind statistics, the wind profile
21 and, climate variations.

22 This work proposes an analytical method to characterize wind resource. Final product is
23 a wind chart containing useful wind information that can be applied to any offshore
24 sites. Using long-term time series of meteorological variables (e.g. wind speed and
25 direction at different heights), the methodology is applied to five pilot sites in different
26 countries along European Atlantic corridor and it is used to describe and compare
27 offshore wind behavior.

28
29 **1. Introduction**

30 Offshore wind in Europe is concentrated in the North Sea and the Baltic Sea. This fact
31 is due to the characteristics of these northern seas: a depth of no more than 60 meters
32 and continuous persistence of high marine winds. The wide area of low depth allows the
33 foundation of turbines directly to seabed with monopiles or jackets and the favorable
34 winds provide a simple wind energy potential. European future of offshore wind energy
35 is based in the Atlantic corridor the Mediterranean Sea and the Black Sea, taking into
36 account countries as Ireland, France or Spain.

37 These regions have completely different characteristics than northern European seas. In
38 the Atlantic region, continental shelf has deep depths and wind farms must be sited far
39 shore (more than 20 km) looking for great wind energy potential. These two
40 characteristics are the main challenges offshore wind industry should face in the future.
41 The other main challenge is the development of floating platforms technology. The
42 purpose of them is to be able to reach higher wind energy potential levels without
43 increasing too much the investment.

44 The costs of an offshore wind farm are considerably higher than those of an onshore one
45 and future locations will need greater investments. The best wind assessment is needed
46 in terms of reducing the uncertainty of these investments.

47 The statistical analysis from long enough wind time series is the first step to do a
48 viability assessment as a filter of different potential locations (Sempreviva et al., 2008).
49 Several features are relevant to evaluate the viability of an offshore wind farm from the
50 wind characteristics, such as the wind distribution (Morgan et al., 2011, Carta et al.,
51 2009, Jaramillo et al., 2004), the extreme wind events (Duroñana et al., 2007), the wind
52 variability thorough the time or the vertical wind profile.

53 Historically, the Weibull distribution has generally been accepted to represent the
54 statistical structure of the wind speed probability density function, particularly over
55 water surfaces (e.g. Pavia and O'Brien, 1986; Monahan, 2006). Extreme winds,
56 associated to a specific return period (e.g. 50-yr wind return level) and wind speed at a
57 particular height is usually required for design purposes. Long-term climate variations
58 provides information about the possible changes on wind efficiency due to seasonality
59 or larger time scales variations, however, a least one year of continuous monitoring of
60 wind speed is used in practice to estimate wind characteristics.

61 The main goal of this paper is to develop an integrated methodology to characterize
62 local wind resource by means of a wind chart. The methodology has been integrated in
63 package coded in Matlab. The package has been applied over five locations along the
64 European Atlantic corridor and the obtained wind charts provide useful info about the
65 offshore wind.

66

67 The paper is arranged as follows. Some basic concepts about wind properties are
68 explained in section 2. In section 3, the methodology is outlined, putting special
69 emphasis on input data, wind distribution, wind profile and wind variability. In section
70 4, some applications of the wind chart for five study sites are shown. Finally, some
71 conclusions are provided.

72

73 **2. Basic Concepts**

74 The characterization of wind resource entails several statistics commonly used for
75 geophysical variables, such as directional description or basic climatologies. Two
76 features are, however, of particular interest to evaluate offshore wind energy resource:
77 wind distribution and wind profile. The former is important to understand the
78 probability of occurrence of different wind speeds, providing statistics and extremes
79 (maxima and minima values). The latter is obtained to understand the wind vertical
80 variation from sea surface to the first atmospheric 200 meters in order to evaluate the
81 potential wind power at a specific hub height. The relationship between wind speed (u)
82 and wind power (P) shows the importance of accurate wind speed assessment. Wind
83 power is the time rate of change in kinetic energy (KE) due to air stream per unit area
84 hence proportional to the third power of the wind speed.

$$85 \quad P = \frac{dKE}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} \rho u^3 \quad , \quad (1)$$

86 where ρ is the air density.

87

88

89

90 2.1 Wind Distribution

91 In order to calculate wind power from a specific wind turbine design over a range of
 92 wind speed values, a generalized expression of the distribution is required for the
 93 probability density function (PDF). The Weibull distribution function has demonstrated
 94 to fit quite well to wind speed data (Frechet, 1927, Rosslin and Rammler, 1933),
 95 especially over water surfaces (Pavia and O'Brien, 1986; Menéndez et al., 2013). The
 96 Weibull PDF with two parameters (k, λ), can be expressed as:

97

$$f(x; \lambda, k) = \begin{cases} 0, & x < 0 \\ \frac{k}{\lambda} \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^{k-1} e^{-(x/\lambda)^k}, & x \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

98 where λ is the scale parameter which is related to the mean of the distribution and k is
 99 the dimensionless shape parameter and it describes the spread of the distribution.
 100 Rayleigh distribution can be used as a simpler model to characterize wind distribution if
 101 the value of the shape parameter k is approximately two.

102 Different estimators of Weibull parameters λ and k can be used (Monahan, 2006), such
 103 as i) estimates obtained using sample estimates of $\text{mean}(\ln x)$ and $\text{std}(\ln x)$; ii)
 104 maximum likelihood estimates and iii) estimates from some approximations, using
 105 sample estimates of $\text{mean}(x)$ and $\text{std}(x)$. Negligible differences have been found on
 106 estimated parameters for large sample sizes (Pryor et al., 2004), therefore, in this case,
 107 the parameters are estimated by the maximum likelihood method.

108

109 A classical theorem in extreme value theory (Coles, 2001) states that the limit
 110 distribution of properly normalized maxima is the generalized extreme value (GEV)
 111 family of distributions. The GEV extreme distribution combines three simpler
 112 distributions into a single form, allowing a continuous range of possible shapes that
 113 includes all three of the simpler distributions: types I, II, and III. Types I, II, and III
 114 families are also known as the Gumbel, Frechet and 3-parameter Weibull distributions,
 115 respectively. We propose the use of the adaptable GEV distribution to characterize the
 116 extreme wind speeds associated to extreme meteorological events. Moreover, GEV
 117 allows the estimations of wind speed associated to a high return period (e.g. 50yr wind
 118 speed return level). The PDF of the GEV distribution, with location parameter μ , scale
 119 parameter σ , and shape parameter $k \neq 0$ is:

120

$$f(x; \mu, \sigma, k) = \left(\frac{1}{\sigma}\right) \exp\left(-\left(1 + k \frac{(x - \mu)}{\sigma}\right)^{-\frac{1}{k}}\right) \left(1 + k \frac{(x - \mu)}{\sigma}\right)^{-1 - \frac{1}{k}}, \quad (3)$$

121

122 defined on $\{1 + k (x - \mu) / \sigma\} > 0$.

123 The shape parameter define the upper tail distribution behaviour. $k > 0$ corresponds to
 124 the distribution Type II (heavy tail of the Fréchet domain of attraction) while $k < 0$
 125 corresponds to the Type III (bounded tail of Weibull domain of attraction). For $k = 0$,
 126 corresponding to the Type I- Gumbel case, the PDF is:

$$f(x|0, \mu, \sigma) = \left(\frac{1}{\sigma}\right) \exp\left(-\exp\left(-\frac{(x - \mu)}{\sigma}\right) - \frac{(x - \mu)}{\sigma}\right) \quad (4)$$

127

128 **2.2 Wind Profile**

129 Wind speed at a specific height is needed to design wind turbines and wind farms.
 130 There are two sources that can provide wind information at several heights of interest
 131 for wind energy industry: in-situ measurements from meteorological masts, LIDAR and
 132 SODAR technologies, and simulated data from 3-D atmospheric numerical models.
 133 Vertical resolution of available data do not always agree with hub height and design
 134 necessities, thus mathematical wind profile expressions are usually fitted to data in
 135 order to evaluate wind speed at a particular hub height.

136 Wind profile is mainly determined by the surface roughness characteristics (i.e.
 137 frictional drag), the heat transfer, and the evaporation process. These factors are
 138 produced by the interaction between air masses with sea surface and the atmospheric
 139 boundary layer (ABL) thickness, and describe three situations of the atmospheric
 140 stability:

141 i) Convective or unstable which is generated from heat transfer from warm ground
 142 surface. ; ii) Stable, typically from cooling of the surface at night; and iii) Neutral,
 143 where the flow can be characterized by the combination of wind shear and no
 144 convection.

145 Some research in this field resulted in empirical wind profile expressions. They all start
 146 from the same point:

147

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial z} = \frac{u_*}{Kl} \quad (5)$$

148

149 Proposed by Panofsky (1973), where u is the wind speed, z is the height, u^* is the
 150 friction velocity, l is scale length and K is the von Karman constant (~ 0.4).

151 After some assumptions (more details in Peña et al., 2008), wind speed at the ABL is
 152 obtained by:

153

$$u = \frac{u_*}{k} \left[\ln\left(\frac{z}{z_0}\right) - \psi_m\left(\frac{z}{L}\right) \right] \quad (6)$$

154 where z_0 is the roughness length and ψ_m is an atmospheric stability function depending
 155 on height z and the Obukhov length L . ψ_m function describes the convective properties
 156 of the air mass.

157 Wind energy industry works always within the first meters of the ABL. Although wind
158 speed variations can be noticed depending on the atmospheric stability, they can be
159 consider negligible within the height range wind industry works in (Holstag, 1984).
160 Some simplifications can be made to the complex expressions derived from expression
161 (6), , resulting in the logarithmic wind profile (Tennekes, 1973):
162

$$u = \frac{u_*}{k} \ln \left(\frac{z}{z_0} \right) \quad (7)$$

163

164 In order to simplify as much as possible, wind industry uses the potential wind profile.
165 The potential wind profile, also named wind power law, resumes every physical
166 information in only one parameter (Hsu et al., 1994), but it fits well to data in the first
167 meters of the ABL (Gryning et al., 2007). All physic information is included in the
168 parameter α , reducing the number of parameters to estimate into two, the wind speed at
169 reference height (i.e. 10 meters) and the exponent parameter α :

$$u = u_{ref} \left(\frac{z}{z_{ref}} \right)^\alpha \quad (8)$$

170

171 There are several estimations methods to obtain the α -parameter value. Least-squares
172 technique is often used in wind energy field because of its simplicity. In this case, a
173 heterocedastic regression model is applied (more details, Mínguez et al., (2012)).
174

174

175 **3. Local Offshore Wind Resource Characterization**

176 The developed methodology in this paper tries to characterize local offshore wind based
177 on different statistical analysis. Figure 1 shows the flowchart of the proposed method.
178 First, a wind record long enough to characterize wind climatologies is required. Second,
179 several statistics are estimated to evaluate the wind resource. We consider special
180 emphasis must be taken on the following features for a wind characterization: i) long-
181 term and extreme long-term distribution, ii) wind profile and iii) climate variability.

182 The proposed methodology aims to determine potential wind energy at a specific
183 location, providing required info to evaluate design conditions (e.g. optimal rotor
184 height) and efficiency of a possible wind farm. Long-term and extreme distributions are
185 based on Weibull and GEV distributions, respectively. In order to understand local wind
186 distribution, the empirical histogram, the PDF, and the cumulative distribution function
187 (CDF) are represented in the wind chart. The return level plot is included in the wind
188 chart as well, providing wind return level estimates and their 95% confidence intervals.
189 Wind profile and its uncertainty are also represented for the first 200 meters. The
190 atmospheric stability described in section 2 determines the obtained wind profile shape.
191 In order to analyze efficiency, the climate variability is taken into account. Seasonal
192 variability is shown using probability wind roses for each season and monthly box-plots
193 of wind speed. The inter-annual variability can be evaluated from wind energy power
194 and air and sea temperature time series during the length of the available records.

195 The integrated methodology is developed in package coded in Matlab®. Matlab® (a
196 registered trademark of The Mathworks, Inc.) is a high-performance language for
197 technical computing, well-known and diffused within the scientific community. It offers

198 advanced data visualization and analysis tools in an easy-to-use environment. The main
199 script (*WindChart.m*) is provided in this work in an annex. *WindChart.m* provides a
200 summarized set of figures and data. It is designed based on functions for each described
201 statistical analysis. The integrated code reduces computational time and allows the users
202 the possibility to study several locations in a short period of time.

203

204 **3.1 Input Data**

205 30-year period is often used to characterize “climate normals” in atmospheric science;
206 instead, in the wind energy community shorter periods are often use (Sempreviva et al.,
207 2008). Wind climatology must be complete in order to portray accurately the annual
208 cycle of wind speed and long enough to be able to account inter-annual variations,
209 however, collection of homogeneous offshore wind data is a challenging problem.
210 Observations from ships are good qualitatively but they suffer from ship motions and
211 they are sparse in space and discontinuous in time. Anchored buoys are sparse offshore
212 in time and affected by wave’s roughness. Meteorological masts are used in order to
213 measure wind speed at different heights (Guanche et al., 2011) but they are sparse
214 offshore, in time and space. Satellite scatterometers offer well-spatially distributed data
215 but short records and irregular in time and space. State-of-the-art atmospheric models
216 are often used to perform global reanalysis. Global reanalysis assimilate meteorological
217 data and reproduce the physical processes for the atmosphere, providing plausible states
218 of the atmosphere, compatible with observations. Some examples of popular reanalyses
219 are Era-Interim (Dee and Uppala, 2009) or CFSR (Saha et al., 2010). Global reanalysis
220 cannot detect meso- and micro-scale phenomena due to their low resolution (coarse
221 representation of orography and land-mask) and, therefore, cannot be used in local wind
222 resource assessment (Menendez et al., 2011). An alternative to solve this problem is
223 coupling Limited Area Models (LAMs), which can be run on small areas of interest
224 usually at the mesoscale resolution (from 5 km up to 100 km).

225 In this work, the European regional atmospheric hindcast, named SeaWind II, has been
226 used (more details in Menendez et al., 2013). SeaWind II is a daily re-forecast covering
227 the whole Mediterranean and Atlantic European region, providing wind-related
228 variables with hourly frequency. SeaWind II is obtained by the mesoscale limited-area
229 atmospheric model WRF (Skamarock et al., 2008) nested into ERA-Interim reanalysis
230 data for the period 1989-2010.

231 Wind speed and direction at the five lower model levels (approximately: 15, 40, 75, 115
232 and 190 meters height), surface wind and air/sea temperature from SeaWind II at hourly
233 time scale has been used. In particular, five locations have been analyzed: Galway
234 (Ireland, Lat: 53.1047°; Lon: -10.0253°), Bristol (UK, Lat: 51.1653°; Lon: -4.6347°), La
235 Rance (France, Lat: 48.7213°; Lon: -2.1341°), Santander (Spain, Lat: 43.5094°; Lon: -
236 3.8235°) and Lisbon (Portugal, Lat: 38.5312°; Lon: -9.5522°). Figure 2 shows the
237 spatial domain of SeaWind II and the five selected study-sites.

238

239 **3.2 Long-term Wind Distribution and Extreme Characterization**

240 The PDF and the CDF are shown to provide information of the long-term distribution.
241 The PDF plot contains the empirical histogram from the data and the fitted Weibull
242 distribution.

243 The histogram plot is developed combining two Matlab functions: *hist* and *bar* from
244 *Specialized plotting toolbox*. *Hist* returns the absolute frequency of a number of bins
245 specified. *Bar* takes the output of *Hist* and display in a bar-graph the elements of the
246 first argument (in this case this argument is converted into probability).

247 The Matlab function *wblfit* from the *statistical toolbox* is used to obtain the weibull
248 estimated parameters showed in equation (2). *wblfit* returns the maximum likelihood
249 estimates, *parmhat*, of the parameters of the Weibull distribution given the values in the
250 vector data, which must be positive. *parmhat* is a two-element row vector: *parmhat*(1)
251 estimates the λ parameter, and *parmhat*(2) estimates the k parameter. Then, both PDF
252 and Weibull fit are plotted together facilitating the analysis process (Figure 3). The
253 mean regime of wind is usually characterized in a probability paper showing the
254 relationship between a specific wind speed value and it gives the area under the
255 PDF from minus infinity to x . The CDF is shown in a Weibull probability plot. The
256 corresponding wind speed of a specific probability is a required data of a wind farm
257 design.

258 The estimation of wind speed return levels (i.e. wind speed associated to the 50 year
259 return period) is also a required statistic for design engineering applications such as
260 offshore wind turbine load cases. The calculation of extreme quantiles is applied to
261 statistical models based on Extreme value theory. The extreme model is based on the
262 GEV family of distributions. The extreme wind distribution is obtained from maximum
263 values of the wind speed time series. The selection of annual maxima from the hourly
264 time series of wind speed is obtained from *maximatempfunction* function. In a second
265 step, *FuncAutoAdjust* is used. This function calculates GEV distribution using the
266 maximum likelihood method. A non-stationary model can be also fitted from this
267 function (more details in Mínguez et al., 2010). Finally, the return level plot is obtained
268 from *AnnualAggregateQuantiles* Matlab function using a confidence interval at 0.05
269 level. Confidence interval level is assessed from Delta method (Rice, 1994). Figure 4
270 shows the return level plot of the fitted GEV model from Santander wind time series.
271 The 50-year return level wind speed is the most common used value. Standards propose
272 this wind speed as the main design parameter for offshore wind turbines and offshore
273 structures.

274

275 **3.3 Wind Profile**

276 The most common available wind variable is the wind speed at 10m height. Wind
277 profile reconstruction is, therefore, required to be able to extrapolate wind speed from
278 10 meters to the design hub height (80-100 meters). Wind expressions can be used in
279 two different ways: i) extrapolating wind speed from a height to another or, ii) fitting an
280 empirical wind expression to field measurements when two or more measurements are
281 able at different heights.

282 The wind profile expression selected for this purpose is potential wind profile
283 (expression 8). In order to take into account the variability of the standard deviation of
284 wind speed at different heights, an heterocedastic regression model is used. The goal of
285 the wind profile figure is to show the mean, the quartiles and the standard deviation of
286 the profile at different heights in an easy way. Figure 5 shows an example. Twenty
287 years of hourly data are analyzed in this figure from the available values at X_1 , x_2 ,
288heights of the record.

289 Function *outlierfilterRNoCte.m* automatically detects the presence of outliers for a
290 confidence level alpha and considering different regression and residual variance
291 models identified by ID. The method first estimates the optimal parameters of the
292 regression model maximizing the log-likelihood function, then calculates the
293 normalized residuals and finally locates data which could be considered as outlier
294 (Minguez et al., 2012).

295

296 **3.4 Climate Variability**

297 The seasonal boxplot figure (Figure 6) is used to characterize the within a year
298 variability of wind intensity. The information provides from this statistical analysis
299 helps to evaluate changes on wind energy efficiency through the seasons. *Boxplot* is a
300 statistical graph that is coded in a Matlab function from the statistics toolbox. The
301 boxplot matlab function displays statistical data from a matrix. In this case, data was
302 organized in a dimension matrix (N, 12), where N is the number of rows. Wind time
303 series is catalogued in twelve columns, each of them corresponds to a within a year
304 month.. The number of rows N, depends on the number of the largest vector. On each
305 box plot, the central mark is the median (red line), the edges of the box are the 25th and
306 75th percentiles (blue box), the whiskers (black line) extend to the data outside the
307 upper and lower quartiles indicating sample variability, and the unusual values distant
308 from other values (outliers) are displayed individually. Points are drawn as outliers if
309 they are larger than $q_3 + w(q_3 - q_1)$ or smaller than $q_1 - w(q_3 - q_1)$, where $w=1.5$ and
310 q_1 and q_3 are the 25th and 75th percentiles, respectively. Figure 6 shows the seasonal
311 variability of wind speed at Santander pilot-site. Maximum winds occur in autumn. The
312 inter-quartile range shows a greater variability for February, April, September and
313 November than in the rest of months. The median value in winter is 7.5 m/s but in
314 summer it decreases to 5.5 m/s.

315 Two time series provide extra information in the wind chart, one is representing sea and
316 air temperature, two main factors to determine atmospheric stability (Figure 7, upper
317 panel). The theoretical wind power (P) has been estimated from the hourly time series
318 as described on equation (1).The illustration of the figures 6 and 7 provides useful
319 information about the profitability of the pilot site since the seasonal and inter-annual
320 variability can be observed. For the showed example, temperature distribution is very
321 regular during the whole time series. It can be seen that only during the summer period
322 the air temperature is higher than sea surface temperature. This means that most of time
323 the atmospheric stability corresponds to unstable conditions. Wind resource in this
324 location reached a maximum value during the year 2000, but normally it cannot reach
325 $10,000 \text{ w/m}^2$.

326 The wind roses section of the wind chart contains graphical information about the wind
327 speed and direction distribution at 90 m height. Using a polar coordinate system two
328 different types of wind roses have been represented taking the complete wind time
329 series period (1989-2010). The standard wind rose frequency (Figure 8) shows the
330 frequency of winds blowing from specific wind directional sectors, with colour bands
331 showing wind speed ranges. The wind rose frequency is especially useful to determine
332 the direction of the prevailing wind. The Matlab function, *iha_wind_rose*, for the
333 intensity rose is based on the *wind_rose* function, available on Mathworks (MMA,
334 2007).The resulting figure of the application of this wind rose frequency to Santander
335 pilot site shows that the most probable winds come from the west. Their probability of

336 occurrence is approximately 35% and these western winds reach the highest wind
337 speeds. It can be seen that eastern winds are the less common.

338 The probability wind rose represents information of the polar histogram of the winds by
339 plotting the density of data. Unusual values associated to extreme wind can be,
340 therefore, observed from this type of rose graph. The Matlab function
341 *ProbabilisticWindRose* is developed for probabilistic roses. This function assesses the
342 amount of wind states in each directional partition and the probability of occurrence for
343 each of them with respect to the total amount. Figure 9 shows the probability wind rose
344 at Santander location for each season. In this figure, the probability for each wind state,
345 defined by its wind speed and wind direction, is plotted in 360°. Higher probability for
346 wind speed over 15 m/s and a wider directional spread can be observed during autumn
347 and winter.

348

349 **4. Case Studies**

350 The integrated methodology to characterize offshore wind resource is applied to the five
351 pilot sites, described in input data section, along the European Atlantic corridor. The
352 obtained wind charts are show from figures 10 to 14.

353 Wind roses show that the dominant wind at Lisbon pilot-site (Figure 14) blows from
354 the Northwhereas the principal wind direction of the rest locations is Southwest or
355 West. This is related to the latitude of each pilot site and the incoming direction of the
356 storms.The probability of the seasonal wind roses shows a common pattern for the
357 North Atlantic coasts. All analyzed sites concentrates higher directional variability
358 during the winter and autumn storminess seasons. Southern winds are more frequent
359 and energetic during these two seasons yet. Lisbon pilot site shows the larger
360 directional variability with Western and Southern winds appearing during winter
361 seasons. In contrast, wind speed decreases and directions are less variable during
362 spring and summer seasons.

363 Boxplots figures show a similar intra-annual behavior in Galway, Bristol and La Rance
364 with less median, 25% percentile and 75% percentile values during the summer. Wider
365 interquartilic range describes winter period in these locations. This phenomenon also
366 happens in Santanderlocation (Figure XX) but the values associated to the median and
367 percentiles are lower. Lisbon has a different characteristic, with a more homogeneous
368 behavior during the year.

369 Regarding the long-term wind distribution, the higher weibull λ parameter corresponds
370 with Galway (western Ireland, figure 10) which estimated λ parameter reaches 12.26. It
371 indicates that Galway is the most exposed analyzed site. The estimated weibull λ
372 parameter for the other sites it is: 10.985 in Bristol, 10.628 in La Rance, 8.7037 in
373 Santander, and 9.3994 in Lisbon. Parameter k is 2.422 in Galway, 2.3893 in Bristol,
374 2.3903 in La Rance, 2.0602 in Santander and 2.5249 in Lisbon.

375 Galway, Bristol and La Rance (figures 11, 12, 13, respectively) have quite similar wind
376 roses due to their latitudinal proximity. This fact is due to they are affected from similar
377 marine atmospheric mesoscale patterns. Santander has also a south inland wind
378 direction component.

379 A wind speed of 10 m/s can be considered a large mean value for offshore wind energy
380 and it has a probability associated in the CDF of 0.75 in Galway, 0.8 in Bristol, 0.8 in
381 La Rance, 0.9 in Santander and 0.9 in Lisbon. This fact shows that northern sites are

382 better locations for offshore wind farms. Another relevant parameter for designing
383 purposes, the 50 return level wind speed, is 30m/s in Galway, 26 m/s in Britol, 25.5 in
384 La Rance, 26.5 in Santander and 21.5 in Lisbon.

385 Air and sea temperatures have a similar seasonal behavior for all the analyzed locations
386 but different mean values. Wind power time series are similar in Bristol and La Rance.
387 These two locations and Lisbon have the lowest peak values. Santander and Galway
388 reaches higher values, such as the peak value that can be seen in Santander during the
389 year 2000. The estimated alpha power coefficient of the wind profile are 0.055 in
390 Galway, 0.064 in Bristol, 0.057 in La Rance, 0.049 in Santander and 0.048 in Lisbon.

391

392 **5. Conclusions**

393 A methodology that integrates statistical techniques to characterize offshore wind and a
394 wind energy potential estimation has been developed. This methodology was developed
395 using Matlab code and the results are shown in a Wind Chart that facilitates their
396 interpretation. This methodology is supposed to be used during the first decision steps.

397 Taking into account the relevant parameters that characterize wind energy is necessary:
398 the long-term distribution, extreme wind events, wind vertical profile and understanding
399 wind variability, at least at seasonal and interannual time scales.

400 Five pilot sites along the European Atlantic corridor have been analyzed. Wind
401 assessment show similar patterns on eastern North Atlantic coasts, with a common West
402 direction and higher directional and energetic winds during autumn and winter seasons.

403

404

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411 **References**

- 412 Carta J.A., Ramírez P., Velázquez S., 2009. A review of wind speed probability
413 distributions used in wind energy analysis: Case studies in the Canary Islands.
414 *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. Volume 13. pp 933-955.
- 415 Coles, S. G., 2001. *An Introduction to Statistical Modelling of Extreme Values*.
416 Springer, 208 pp.
- 417 Dee D.P., Uppala S. 2009. Variational bias correction of satellite radiance data in the
418 ERA-Interim reanalysis. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, pp
419 1830-1841.
- 420 Duroñana V., Sterling M., Baker C.J., 2007. An analysis of extreme non-synoptic
421 winds. *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics* 95, 1007-1027.
- 422 EWEA. «Report 2012.» 2012.
- 423 Fréchet, M. 1927 Sur la loi de probabilité de l'écart maximum. *Ann.Soc.Polon.Math* 6,
424 pp 93.
- 425 Gryning S.E., Batchvarova E., Brummer B., Jorgensen H., Larsen S. 2007. On the
426 extension of the wind profile over homogeneous terrain beyond the surface boundary
427 layer. *Boundary-Layer_Meteorol* 124, pp 251-268.
- 428 Guancho R, Vidal C, Piedra A, Losada I. 2011 IDERMAR METEO. Offshore wind
429 assessment at high and very high water depths. *OCEANS, IEEE-Spain (OCEANS, 2011*
430 *IEEE-Spain, 1-8)*, pp 1-8.
- 431 Holtslag, AAM.. 1984 Estimates of diabatic wind speed profiles from near-surface
432 weather observations. *Boundary-Layer-Meteorol* 29, pp 225-250.
- 433 Hsu, S. A., Eric A. Meindl, David B. Gilhousen, 1994. Determining the Power-Law
434 Wind-Profile Exponent under Near-Neutral Stability Conditions at Sea. *J. Appl.*
435 *Meteor.*, 33, 757-765.
- 436 Jaramillo O.A., Borja M.A. 2004. Wind speed analysis in La Ventosa, Mexico: a
437 bimodal probability distribution case. *Renewable Energy*. Volume 29, Issue 10, pp
438 1613-1630
- 439 Menéndez M., Tomás A., Camus P., García-Díez, M., Fita, Fernández, L., Méndez, F.J. ,
440 Losada I.J. 2011 A methodology to evaluate regional-scale offshore wind energy
441 resources. *OCEANS'11 IEEE*, Spain.
- 442 Menendez M., M. Garcia-Diez, L. Fita, J. Fernández, F. J. Mendez, J. M. Gutiérrez,
443 2013. High-resolution sea wind hindcasts over the Mediterranean area. *Climate*
444 *Dynamics*. DOI 10.1007/s00382-013-1912-8.
- 445 Mínguez, R. , Méndez, F.J. , Izaguirre, C., Menéndez, M. , Losada I.J. 2010 Pseudo-
446 optimal parameter selection of non-stationary generalized extreme value models for
447 environmental variables. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, Volume 25, Issue 12,
448 December pp 1592-1607.
- 449 Mínguez, R., Reguero, B. G. , Luceño, A. , Méndez F. J. 2012 Regression Models for
450 Outlier Identification (Hurricanes and Typhoons) in Wave Hindcast Databases. *Journal*
451 *of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology* 29, pp 267-285.
- 452 MMA. «Wind Rose Matlab function.» Mathworks (www.mathworks.com). 2007.

- 453 Monahan, S. H. 2006 The Probability Distribution of Sea Surface Wind Speeds. Part I:
454 Theory and SeaWinds Observations. American Meteorological Society pp 497-520.
- 455 Morgan E.C., Lackner M., Vogel R.M., Baise L.G. 2011. Probability distributions for
456 offshore wind speeds. Energy Conversion and Management. Volume 52, pp 15-26.
- 457 Panofsky, H. 1973 Tower micrometeorology. In: Haugen DA (ed) Workshop on
458 Micrometeorology, American Meteorological Society, pp 151-176.
- 459 Pavia, Edgar G. and O'Brien, James J. 1986 Weibull Statistics of Wind Speed over the
460 Ocean. Journal of Climate and Applied Meteorology, pp 1324-1332.
- 461 Peña, Alfredo., Gryning, Sven-Erik. 2008 Charnock's Roughness Length Model and
462 Non-Dimensional Wind Profiles Over the Sea. Boundary-Layer-Meteorol 128, pp 191-
463 203.
- 464 Pryor, S. C., M. Nielsen, R. J. Barthelmie, J. Mann, 2004. Can Satellite Sampling of
465 Offshore Wind Speeds Realistically Represent Wind Speed Distributions? Part II:
466 Quantifying Uncertainties Associated with Distribution Fitting Methods. J. Appl.
467 Meteor., 43, 739–750.
- 468 Rice, A.L. 1994 Forty years of land-locked oceanography; the Institute of
469 Oceanographic Sciences at Wormley, 1953–1995. Endeavour, Volume 18, Issue 4, pp
470 137-146.
- 471 Rosin, P., y E. Rammler. 1993. The Laws Governing the Fineness of Powdered Coal.
472 Journal of the Institute of Fuel 7, pp 29–36.
- 473 Saha, Suranajana, and Coauthors, 2010. The NCEP Climate Forecast System
474 Reanalysis. Bull.Amer.Meteor.Soc.,91, pp 1015-1057.
- 475 Sempreviva A.M., Barthelmie R.J., Pryor S.C., 2008. Review of Methodologies for
476 Offshore Wind Resource Assessment in European Seas. Surv. Geophys 29, pp 471-497.
- 477 Skamarock WC, Klemp JB, Dudhia J, Gill DO, Baker DM, Duda MG, Huang XY,
478 Wang W, Powers JG, 2008. A description of the advanced research WRF version 3.
479 NCAR Tech Note NCAR/TN-475+STR p 125.
- 480 Tennekes, H., 1973 The Logarithmic Wind Profile. Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences,
481 pp 234-238.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the developed methodology.

Figure 2. Spatial domain of SeaWind II database and the analyzed pilot-sites.

Figure 3. (left) Wind speed histogram, and Weibull PDF. (Right) Wind speed CDF or Mean Regime.

Figure 4. Return level plot of wind speed at Santander location.

Figure 5. Estimated wind Profile

Figure 6. Wind Boxplot. Location: Santander

Figure 7. (top) Air & Sea Temperature time series. (bottom) Wind Power time series.

Figure 8. Wind rose at Santander study-site.

Figure 9. Seasonal probability wind roses. Location: Santander